

Self-Managed Finger Grip Rehabilitation Device

(Peralatan Rehabilitasi Pengurusan Kendiri Cengkaman Jari)

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ABSTRACT

There has been a rapid increase in the past decade in the numbers of robotic assistive rehabilitation device that are being developed. These devices are used to assist patients in speedy recovery through personalization and precision in the exercise parameter setting. Through this approach, rehabilitation aims to improve the quality of life among patients by providing efficient and effective rehabilitation support. The second advantage in this approach is providing a home base service rather than expecting the patients to travel to the rehabilitation centre for each session with the supervision of their therapist. This opportunity allows the patient in participating regular exercise schedule and resolve the high transportation cost and time demand. This study proposed a self-managed rehabilitation device for finger grip exercise among Ischemic Stroke patients. This project is divided into two phases. Phase one focuses on the hardware design and development that going to be attached to the patient's hand. The microcontroller-based device comprises of control mechanism, wireless data transfer and local storage using SD card. Whereas, phase 2 focuses on mobile application development as the interface medium for the users. Completion of both the phases has resulted in a self-managed handheld finger grip exercise device with timing, strength and frequency controller and online prescription and monitoring by the therapist. In this study, the researchers have established the control and communication mechanism and the next phase of the study is to identify the best material and user experience-based design in ensuring the usability and sustainability of the device among ischemic stroke patients.

Keywords: Finger Grip; Rehabilitation; Self-Managed; Internet of Things; Micro-controller

ABSTRAK

Terdapat peningkatan pesat dalam jumlah penghasilan alat pemulihan rehabilitasi berbantuan robotik. Peranti ini digunakan untuk membantu pesakit pulih dengan lebih cepat melalui proses personalisasi dan ketepatan dalam pengatur parameter latihan. Melalui pendekatan ini, pemulihan dapat meningkatkan kualiti hidup individu dengan memberikan sokongan pemulihan yang cekap dan berkesan. Kelebihan kedua dalam pendekatan ini adalah menyediakan perkhidmatan rehabilitasi di rumah daripada mengharap pesakit pergi ke pusat pemulihan untuk setiap sesi dengan pengawasan ahli terapi mereka. Peluang ini memungkinkan pesakit untuk mengikuti jadual latihan biasa dan menjimatkan kos pengangkutan dan masa. Kajian ini mencadangkan alat pemulihan yang dikendalikan sendiri untuk senaman cengkaman jari di kalangan pesakit Stroke Iskemia. Projek ini terbahagi kepada dua fasa. Fasa pertama memberi tumpuan kepada reka bentuk dan pembangunan perkakasan yang akan dipasangkan di tangan pesakit. Peranti berasaskan mikropengawal terdiri daripada mekanisme kawalan, pemindahan data tanpa wayar dan penyimpanan data menggunakan kad SD. Manakala, fasa 2 memfokuskan pada pembangunan aplikasi mudah alih sebagai medium antara muka untuk interkasi pengguna. Penyelesaian kedua-dua fasa ini telah menghasilkan alat senaman cengkaman jari yang diuruskan sendiri dengan pengatur masa, kekuatan dan kekerapan serta preskripsi dan pemantauan dalam talian oleh ahli terapi. Dalam kajian ini, penyelidik telah menetapkan mekanisme kawalan dan komunikasi dan dalam fasa seterusnya kajian ini akan mengenal pasti bahan dan pengalaman pengguna yang terbaik dalam memastikan kebolegunaan dan kesinambungan alat di kalangan pesakit pasca Stroke Iskemia.

Kata Kunci: Cengkaman jari; Rehabilitasi; Sistem sendiri; Internet Pelbagai Benda; Mikropengawal

INTRODUCTION

Rehabilitation is the measures used to help an individual who is experiencing or possibly

experiencing, inability to achieve and maintain normal and optimal function in interaction with their environment. Rehabilitation targets improvements in individual functions and identifies a person's problems and needs, relates problems to factors

related to the individual and the environment, sets necessary goals and exercises, plans, implements measures, and observes improvements and impacts. Recovery through rehabilitation is always a practical practice. The success of the recovery process through rehabilitation largely depends on the skills and experience of the rehabilitation specialist or therapist as well as patient motivation in present setting. The increasing ratio between the patient number and therapist and the life-style has created a need for self-managed rehabilitation. The use of health technology can improve patient outcomes as well as patient satisfaction (Michael Rucker 2020) in the urban setting.

In addition, the use of information technology in rehabilitation can facilitate the current rehabilitation process since therapists cannot gather durable contextual information to perceive the performance and development of patients in the traditional practice. This approach requires a process or ecosystem in which the rehabilitation process and related information can be captured for further analytics (Ami Kalsom Bt. Desa 2017). Customization, personalization and precision are the important measure in self-managed rehabilitation process. This study is focusing in design and developing a finger grip rehabilitation practice among the ischemic post-stroke patients. Precision factoring in the proposed eco-system needs the anatomy and physiology knowledge modeling approach.

Finger grip rehabilitation focuses on the upper limb anatomy. The upper limbs anatomy is divided into 3 main regions. First, is the arm located between the shoulder joint and the elbow. The second is the forearm located between the elbow and the wrist joint and the last hand is located distal to the wrist. The arm consists of a single bone known as the humerus. The forearm consists of two bones known as the ulna and the radius. Hand is made up of 27 bones that are divided into phalanx, metacarpal, and carpal. Hand, arm, and finger movements are important and are often used in daily activities including those involving reaching, grasping, and manipulating activities. The upper limbs have different degrees of freedom and ability in taking different positions. Therefore, to perform a balanced and specific activity, all other parts need to contribute to optimal performance. It is used to pick up objects of different sizes, shapes and coordinate isolated or more complex movements. Figure 1 shows the structure of upper limb.

FIGURE 1. Structure of upper limb

Hands are an important part of the upper part of daily routine for carrying out activities such as washing, drying clothes, carrying heavy objects and others. The hand is made up of bones such as carpal, metacarpal, and phalanx. The wrists and base of the hand are made up of eight small bones. Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4 shows the structure of carpal bones, structure of metacarpal bones and structure of phalanx bones, respectively.

FIGURE 2. Structure of carpal bones

FIGURE 3. Structure of metacarpal bones

FIGURE 4. Structure of phalanx bones

Physical activity is defined as all human movement produced by skeletal muscle action that increases energy production. Physical activity is important to improve and maintain physical fitness.

Rehabilitation training is one of the planned, structured, and repetitive physical activities. It is intended to improve physical fitness. Key indices for physical fitness include cardiorespiratory fitness and muscle strength as well as power. This is to determine the ability to perform physical activities. A patient often wonders about the amount of rehabilitation training and physical activity especially after the patient is discharged from the hospital. There are various types of rehabilitation exercises for patients. Among them are Passive Range of Motion, Active Range of Motion (AROM), Assistive Range of Motion (AAROM), Fine Motor Skills, Strengthening or

Resistance Training, Grip strengthening and brain training. (Cognitive Exercises).

Table 1 shows the Comparison between the latest devices in rehabilitation. Based on table 1, we can conclude most of the latest device does not have a storage element such as SD card or cloud to store the data of rehabilitation session this is a disadvantage since there is not data for the therapist to analyze the progress of patients. Besides, most of the devices do not have a user interface and wireless technology like mobile application or software which helps to monitor the session and easy obtain of data from the hardware without any miscommunication. The types of technology system used are mostly manual which means it done by the patients with the help of the therapist that is less preferable since a patient need to wait for the therapist to carry out their exercise followed by embedded system which is a combination of software and hardware to carry out a specific task that is more preferable in the system.

Table 2 shows a comparison between technologies in rehabilitation. Based on the table 2, the latest technology system is in rehabilitation where most of the technology is carried out manually. There are also technologies that use embedded systems and run with the use of computers. Most of the technologies used do not have a graphical user interface or wireless technology. Finally, the latest rehabilitation technology has no storage element except Motion analysis to store all information or data to be used as research material

TABLE 1. Comparison between the latest devices in rehabilitation

Latest device	Technology System	Type of motor	User interface	Wireless technology / interface communication	Storage element
Cybergrasp	Computer based system	Direct current Motor(x5)	No	Virtual reality(VR)	No
Eggserciser	Manual	No	No	No	No
Finger exoskeleton robot	Embedded system	Stepper motor	No	No	No
Gloreha	Computer based system	Electrical motor (x5)	Computer	RS232	User interface

Gripmaster	Manual	No	No	No	No
Grip pinch exerciser	Manual	No	No	No	No
Handcare	Manual	Direct current Motor (x1)	No	No	No
HWARD	Embedded system	Direct current Motor	No	No	No
Robotic orthotic	Embedded system	Servo motor (4x)	Computer	No	No

TABLE 2. Comparison between the latest technologies in rehabilitation

Latest technology	Technology system	Type of Motor	User interface	Wireless technology / interface communication	Storage element
Robotics	Computer based system	Direct current Motor	No	Virtual Reality (VR)	No
Transcranial magnetic stimulation	Manual	No	No	No	No
Transcranial direct current stimulation (TDCS)	Embedded system	Stepper motor	No	No	No
Motion analysis	Computer based system	Electrical motor	Computer	RS232	User interface
Assistive technology	Manual	No	No	No	No
Musculoskeletal modeling and simulations	Manual	No	No	No	No

Remote control rehabilitation is a process where exercise or training that needs to be done in a rehabilitation center under the supervision of a therapist can be performed in any place such as home or office. This remote-control rehabilitation will have a huge impact on technological developments in rehabilitation and on all patients. Remote control rehabilitation brings many benefits not only for patients but also for rehabilitation experts and therapists such as the cost of

transporting patients to and from the rehabilitation center and the cost of patient treatment is reduced, and limited monitoring time of therapists can be overcome. Therapists are also able to monitor the patient's development and condition from time to time and collect data easily and quickly. Table 3 shows the comparison between rehabilitation programs in rehabilitation centers and rehabilitation programs at home.

TABLE 3. Comparison between rehabilitation programs in rehabilitation centers and rehabilitation programs at home

Criteria	Rehabilitation programs in rehabilitation centers	Rehabilitation programs at home
Rehabilitation duration	Limited time due to increasing number of patients, limited rehabilitation / therapists	Long time because patients can perform exercises according to the suitability of their time
Cost	High costs due to treatment costs and transportation costs	Low cost as patients do not have to go to a rehabilitation center and replace cheaper treatment with a home visit without interrupting the rehabilitation process.
Rehabilitation Team	Training is done under the supervision of rehabilitation / therapy experts. Limited time due to tight schedule	Training is carried out without the supervision of a rehabilitation / therapist and is done on its own.
Frequency of rehabilitation sessions	Patients can perform possible exercises once or 2 times a week only.	Patients can perform exercises on their own time and based on the patient's ability.
Support/Help	Patients need support from family members to follow along to undergo their training. This will interfere with the time and work of family members.	Family members only need to monitor patient rehabilitation sessions.
Transportation	Patients need appropriate transportation based on the conditions for the round trip to the rehabilitation center	Patients do not need transportation

Based on table 3, rehabilitation at home is very suitable for patients nowadays due to the increase in the number of patients which leads to high demand for rehabilitation at home. In addition, with this program, patients can do rehabilitation according to their own time and schedule. Initially, to perform a training session the patient needs to attend a rehabilitation center after making an appointment with a rehabilitation specialist or therapist. This causes the recovery process to take a long time and delays the treatment needed by the patient. This is because rehabilitation centers have limited rehabilitation officers and rehabilitation equipment. Furthermore, a patient does not require help from the family member to carry out the exercise instead they just need to monitor the session done by the patient. In conclusion, to overcome this problem, an effective solution is to establish a home-

based rehabilitation practice that has monitoring that can collect patient data and monitor patient development.

An actuator is a component used in a machine that provides control, limiting movement or position in a mechanism or system that operates by electric current, hydraulic or pneumatic fluid pressure is converted into one energy to another. The use of actuators in finger rehabilitation technology is important for controlling and moving the fingers. The selection of the appropriate type of actuator used in the rehabilitation device is based on size, weight, power, and transmission to the prototype. Table 4 shows the comparison of the types of actuators in terms of their respective advantages and disadvantages.

TABLE 4. Comparison of the types of actuators in terms of their respective advantages and disadvantages.

Type of actuators	Advantages	Disadvantages
Pneumatic	Common skills understood Low cost Easy construction	Only suitable for easy movement Static friction problem Low bandwidth capability.

Hydraulics	Low cost Independent system suitable for remote installation High power density	Inefficient Temperature sensitivity Requires continuous maintenance
Alternating current motor	Easy to install Easy to control Low noise	High maintenance costs Inefficient speed control
Direct current motor	High selectable power factor speed	Cannot operate at low speeds Expensive cost Large size
Servo Motor	Low cost Small size Easy to integrate and control	Complex Damage occurs with constant load

Based on table 4, we can see that every actuator has its advantages and disadvantages. To build a hardware, the size of the actuators and cost plays a big role. For the development of rehabilitation technology, it is important to take priority of the patient condition. Besides, the actuator needs to be efficient and easy to program to have a precise and accurate results.

In this paper, the design for a self-rehabilitation device was built and developed to focus on patients suffering from paralysis and injury to the upper limbs, especially the fingers. In addition, the rehabilitation activities that have been selected to be implemented in this rehabilitation device system are Active Range of Motion (AROM) rehabilitation exercises. This activity is chosen because the paralyzed or injured limbs will move on their own without any help from others and will be propelled by the propulsion system. Next, the servo motor is suitable for integration with the system as well as for prototype construction. The main choice of servo motor as an actuator is because the servo motor is small compared to other actuators. The servo motor also has high durability and can control and make precise rotation spoon. The servo motor is also easy to integrate and control. Finally, this prototype has an embedded system divided into two parts namely hardware and software.

METHODOLOGY

For the development of prototype model of the finger grip involves the development of

hardware. To design the self-managed rehabilitation model application is with the development of a graphical user interface. Hardware development involves microcontroller, servo motor, secure digital card (SD), liquid crystal display (LCD) and real-time clock (RTC) and robotic hands. While for the development of mobile application using MIT app inventor software. The development of this prototype system model also uses Proteus 8 Professional software to build circuit diagrams.

Figure 5 shows the process of how the system works. The system starts with the rehabilitation officer having to enter the prescription settings of patient after entering the patient information in the mobile application designed. The prescription settings will be saved in the SD card in a text format (.txt) file. Next, the SD card will be inserted by the rehabilitation officer into hardware through the SD card reader that is connected to the Arduino Uno microcontroller which has a connection with the servo motor. Once the system has received the prescription then the rehabilitation device activates the servo motor and the rehabilitation session takes place. During the patient's rehabilitation session, each rehabilitation activity will be recorded and stored. This storage process is where a .csv format file will be created and stored in the SD card. Therefore, the information of patient rehabilitation session will be visible to the rehabilitation officer in the mobile application and the patient's progress can be seen when the file in the SD card is downloaded into the computer.

FIGURE 5. Block diagram of the self-managed finger grip rehabilitation system

Figure 6 shows how mobile application is connected to the hardware and each component in the hardware are connected. Prescription data input for the proposed finger grip self-management tool consists of 4 inputs namely rehabilitation period, rehabilitation speed, rehabilitation strength and rest time for rehabilitation.

In the storage unit, the system uses a secure digital card (SD) to store all log data for user prescription data during the recovery session. All data prescription inputs will be set and entered the SD card by the rehabilitation officer. The SD card will be connected to the micro-controller via the SD card shield. For the user interface that will be displayed on the mobile phone, SD card will be connected to the via universal serial bus (USB) to the mobile phone and computer. The central unit of this system is the unit consisting of the microcontroller. The microcontroller in this system serves as the main system. The liquid crystal display (LCD) will be connected to the Arduino Uno microcontroller via an integrated circuit communication interface (I2C). The SD card shield will be connected to the microcontroller via serial peripheral interface (SPI) communication. The microcontroller will also be connected to 5 servo motors. The 5 servo motors will be connected via the micro-controller pulse width modulation pin (PWM). The switch button will be connected via the micro-controller input.

The display unit uses liquid crystals display (LCD) to inform and display activities during the rehabilitation session. This unit consists of 5 servo motors. This servo motor acts as an actuator to control the movement of each finger.

This unit consists of 5 servo motors. Each servo motor for one finger. This servo motor acts as an actuator to control the movement of each finger.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system has a unique and special function where professional therapists can prescribe patient prescription input data through mobile applications and upload to a secure digital card (SD). The system will begin with a professional therapist prescribing patient prescription input data. This prescription input data will be determined based on the patient's recovery and developmental stage.

After the patient's prescription input data is set and uploaded to a secure digital card (SD), the patient simply needs to press the switch button to enable reading of information in a secure digital card (SD), activate all servo motors and subsequently finger movements will result based on patient prescription input. If the patient wants to stop the rehabilitation session, the patient needs to press the off button and the movement of the fingers and servo motor will stop. If the patient does not press the off button, the servo motor will remain active and finger movements will result.

FIGURE 7. Functional block model of finger grip rehabilitation device system

Finger movement is produced when the servo motor pulls the flexor cable and will cause the fingers to bend to the inside temporarily when tightening the extensor cable occurs it will return the finger to its original or normal position. During finger movements, the LCD display will display the activities that take place and all activities will be stored in the SD card so that the rehabilitation officer can see the progress of patient.

Figure 8 (a) shows the user interface application display for prescription settings. Rehabilitation duration: 4 Minutes, rehabilitation strength: 45°, Rehabilitation speed: 120 mbps, rehabilitation rest time: 10 seconds; while figure 8 (b) shows position of each finger before starting and position of each finger in a 45° rehabilitation strength; and finally figure 8 (c) shows the servo motor position before starting and servo motor in rehabilitation strength condition 45°.

Figure 8(d) shows the user interface application display for prescription settings. Rehabilitation duration: 4 Minutes, rehabilitation strength: 90°, Rehabilitation speed: 120 mbps, rehabilitation rest time: 10 seconds; while figure 8 (e) shows position of each finger before starting and position of each finger in a 45° rehabilitation strength; and finally figure 8(f) shows the servo motor position before starting and servo motor in rehabilitation strength condition 90°. Figure 9(a) shows the user interface application display for prescription settings. Rehabilitation duration: 4 Minutes, rehabilitation strength: 135°, Rehabilitation speed: 120 mbps, rehabilitation rest time: 10 seconds; while figure 9(b) shows position of each finger before starting and position of each finger in a 135° rehabilitation strength; and finally figure 9(c) shows the servo motor position before starting and servo motor in rehabilitation strength condition 135°.

FIGURE 8. (a) User interface application display for prescription settings. Rehabilitation duration: 4 Minutes, rehabilitation strength: 45°, Rehabilitation speed: 120 mbps, rehabilitation rest time: 10 seconds; (b) position of each finger before starting and position of each finger in a 45° rehabilitation strength; (c) servo motor position before starting and servo motor in rehabilitation strength condition 45°. (d) User interface application display for prescription settings. Duration: 4 Minutes, Rehabilitation Strength: 90°, Rehabilitation Speed: 120 mbps, Rehabilitation Rest time: 10 seconds; (e) Position of each finger before starting and Position of each finger in a 90° rehabilitation strength; (f) Servo motor position before starting and servo motor in rehabilitation strength condition 90°

FIGURE 9 (a) User interface application display for prescription settings. Duration: 4 Minutes, Rehabilitation Strength: 135°, Rehabilitation Speed: 120 mbps, Rehabilitation Rest time: 10 seconds; (b) Position of each finger before starting and Position of each finger in a 135° rehabilitation strength; (c) Servo motor position before starting and servo motor in rehabilitation strength condition 135°. (d) User interface application display for prescription settings. Duration: 4 Minutes, Rehabilitation Strength: 180°, Rehabilitation Speed: 120 mbps, Rehabilitation Rest time: 10 seconds; (e) Position of each finger before starting and Position of each finger in a 180° rehabilitation strength; (f) Servo motor before starting and servo motor in rehabilitation strength condition 180°.

Figure 9(d) shows the user interface application display for prescription settings. Rehabilitation duration: 4 Minutes, rehabilitation strength: 180°, Rehabilitation speed: 120 mbps, rehabilitation rest time: 10 seconds; while figure 9(e) shows position of each finger before starting and position of each finger in a 180° rehabilitation strength; and finally figure 9(f) shows the servo motor position before starting and servo motor in rehabilitation strength condition 180°.

Mobile application for home-based self-management rehabilitation system has several components. There are 3 sections which are patient information, patient prescription, and patient rehabilitation progress. For the patient information section, the rehabilitation officer must enter the patient's name and id number. For the information and determination section of the patient's prescription, the rehabilitation officer will prescribe the patient's prescription based on the patient's development and condition. For the rehabilitation part of the patient is the information of each rehabilitation session that has been done by the patient. This rehabilitation progress information enters the patient information and click the can show the info of each patient doing rehabilitation activities. Figure 10 shows mobile application for home-based fingerprint monitoring rehabilitation model.

FIGURE 10. Mobile application for home-based fingerprint monitoring rehabilitation model

Figure 11 shows the step to use the mobile application. Firstly, open the finger grip rehabilitation mobile application in the mobile phone. The second step is to enter the patient information and click the "ENTER" FIGURE 12. Patient details.txt fail button. If file does not exist, click the "SAVE" button. This will create a new patient details.txt file

which contains the patient's information. The third step is to click the "ENTER" button to display the patient information, select patient and click "NEXT" button. The fourth and final step is, the patient prescription settings are determined and click the "UPLOAD" button to create a prog.txt file and insert it into the SD card.

FIGURE 11. Steps to use the application system for the self-monitoring finger grip rehabilitation system

FIGURE 12. Patient details.txt fail

Figure 12 shows the patient details.txt fail which is in the mobile phone once it's being created using the mobile application. Figure 13 shows the prog.txt file created using the mobile application based on the prescription given by the therapist.

FIGURE 13. Prescription details.txt fail

Figure 13 shows the programming sample of create data files.csv for display and storage of patient rehabilitation progress. When an officer wants to get information and patient progress, the officer just needs to enter data.csv into the mobile phone and

click "IMPORT" and the information will be displayed on the user interface application. Three criteria are taken to look at the patient's progress, namely the date, month of rehabilitation and start time.

Figure 14 shows the programming sample of create data files.csv for display and storage of patient rehabilitation progress while Figure 15 shows display of patient progress data from the data.csv file in the mobile application. When an officer wants to get information and patient progress, the officer just needs to enter data.csv into the mobile phone and click "IMPORT" and the information will be displayed on the user interface application. Three criteria are taken to look at the patient's progress, namely the date, month of rehabilitation and start time. Finally, figure 16 shows display of patient progress using data.csv file.

FIGURE 14. Programming sample to create data files.csv for display and storage of patient rehabilitation progress

FIGURE 15. Display of patient progress data from the Data.csv file in the mobile application

FIGURE 16. Displays patient progress using Data.csv file

CONCLUSION

This paper presents a self-managed finger grip rehabilitation device that designed for home rehabilitation. This device expected to benefit both the rehabilitation specialist and patient. The proposed system supports to reduce the long process that patient needs to go through for ischemic stroke finger grip recovery. The additional advantage is the parameters integrated to assist in monitoring the progress of the patient with updating options either stored in a SD card or cloud storage. The developed device is expected to be cost efficient, accurate in its

measurement and prediction on the patient recovery details. This device is also expected to serve beyond ischemic stroke patients needs. Patients who are undergoing surgery due to accidents and many other finger related treatments that need rehabilitation to gain back their finger grip strength and confident. A home-based rehab device with personalization and precision expected to provide patients with a better recovery opportunity.

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